

CAREER ADVANCEMENT AND JOB SATISFACTION AMONG NON-ACADEMIC STAFF IN UNIVERSITY SETTINGS AND IMPLICATIONS FOR ETHICAL LEADERSHIP

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Abstract:

Career advancement path of academic staff (also referred to as faculty members in this paper) is well spelt out in ranking for promotion policy guidelines. Emerging academic staff when well oriented into the academic arena, get to know what competences, skills and credentials to work on to move from one level of rank to another, and within how much time. While rank equivalences exist for their counterparts, the non-academic staff's elaborate criteria on how to move from one level to another is usually lacking. Moreover, there are no clear guidelines for rank implications when one migrates from non-academic roles into academic roles. The disparity exists because of various reasons such as: limited financial resources to remunerate growing numbers of non-academic staff, diversity of non-academic careers within universities and unclear appraisal mechanisms among others. Nonetheless, the need to have a career advancement path for non-academic staff is long overdue in addressing a major disparity between personnel of the same institutions. This is primarily an ethical issue in regard to human resource management. Ethical leadership therefore demands that this disparity is addressed even as higher education leadership seeks to create work environments where employees can thrive as they advance in their careers, regardless of their domain of operation, whether academic or non-academic. This paper therefore seeks to review literature on issues related to career advancement/promotion opportunities for non-academic staff, and their implications for ethical academic leadership in university settings. It is hoped that the discussions in this paper will lead to amicable solutions for clear and effective career advancement pathways for non-academic personnel in university settings.

Keywords: career advancement, promotion opportunities, job satisfaction, higher education, non-academic staff, ethical leadership, self-leadership

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1. Introduction

Career advancement is a virtue desired and pursued by all employees regardless of the nature of institution one is employed or their background. Since all healthy employees have an inherent desire to grow in their careers, promotion is expected either as a reward for either loyalty or/and productivity at work. Studies have shown that career advancement is related to job satisfaction. For example, Ssesanga and Garrett (2005) found that lack of promotion opportunities was a contributor to dissatisfaction among academics in two Ugandan universities. Absher (2009) found that minorities in Christian higher education, rated “*opportunity for advancement promotion*”, among other factors, as being significantly more important to them than their Caucasian counterparts (p. 174). The existence of opportunities for promotion has been identified as a factor for job satisfaction globally (Mbogo, 2016; Johnsrud, 2002; Mustapha & Zakaria 2013; Smerek & Peterson 2006; Malik, et al., 2012). Moreover, opportunities for promotion are linked to level of task performance. Edward, et al. (2008) found that there was a negative significant relationship between satisfaction with promotion and task performance. However, some organizations seem not to have a career advancement path for their personnel. Such is the case with higher education institutions with regard to their non-academic staff members.

1.1 Problem Statement

In many universities, career advancement for academic staff is elaborate and personnel can do what it takes to achieve desirable ranks. Nonetheless, academic staff with administrative responsibilities still faces challenges. For example, a study by Mbogo (2011) indicated that faculty without administrative responsibilities were likely to be more satisfied with some aspects of their jobs, including satisfaction with promotion opportunities, than either full time administrators or faculty with administrative responsibilities. This could be explained by lack of adequate time to participate in activities that add value to ranking of academic staff, such as research and publishing. Moreover, the administrative jobs do not provide career paths for growth and advancement by themselves and are short term, yet highly demanding.

In the same study faculty were more satisfied with their work than their counterparts who were non-academic staff, and more specifically, administrators (Mbogo 2015). Studies have shown that administrators in higher education tend to be overwhelmed by work and experience higher levels of burnout than their counterparts who are full time faculty members (Mbogo, 2015; Maslach & Schaufeli, 2009). This could be a result of lower salaries, high workload and lack of promotion opportunities, among other factors (Maslach, 2003). As a result, turnover rates are usually higher among non-academic personnel, sometimes disturbing equilibrium in the smooth running of the educational enterprise that universities seek to enhance.

Wachira (2016) conducted a study to examine factors affecting non-teaching staff development in Kenyan universities. She found that:

“Non-teaching staff development in campuses faced challenges related to skills development. Management lack conception to further training needs for non-teaching staff, lack of any training arrangement or funding extended to middle level non-teaching staff. Staff progression structure path for middle level was not clear, whether it is based on academic qualifications or otherwise. Non-teaching-staff in campuses who acquired additional qualifications on personal effort were not rewarded accordingly. There were various methods used which were not motivating non-teaching staff in campuses, such as additional responsibilities and lack of promotion. There was inadequate number of staff working in the campuses resulting in multi-tasking, lack of advanced skills and competencies.” (p. 127)

Unlike their faculty member counterparts, non-academic staff find themselves remaining in one docket of work all their career life, unless they opt out of higher education contexts. This is one reason for the high turn-over rate of non-academic staff in universities. The predicament has pushed some non-academic staff to take personal initiative for further education in order to improve their chances for better placement. Notably, most of these do not take higher degrees in the area of their lower credentials; they usually change their career paths. Their choices are usually informed by the types of programs offered in their universities where they choose to study. Moreover, their universities usually offer them subsidized tuition fees as staff as well as study time, which is convenient even if they change their study areas. In such scenarios many hope to acquire enough credentials to transition to faculty positions, particularly those who may be middle age or senior adults. This has become preferable to non-academic staff who are cognizant of the promotion opportunities available for faculty members and the opportunity to work longer before retirement at age (currently at 60 for non-academic staff and 70 for academic staff). This paper therefore explores career advancement challenges among non-academic staff in university contexts and its implications on ethical educational leadership in addressing the challenges. The author opines that career advancement requires an integrated approach where ethical leadership works with ethical followership in a context where self-leadership is effectively applied by all.

1.2 Theoretical Framework

This study is underpinned on two theories – the motivation-hygiene theory and the expectancy theory. The motivation-hygiene theory (Herzberg (1959) indicates what organizations need to do to provide intrinsic motivation while working on contextual issues that could trigger dissatisfaction among staff. The factors of motivation (satisfiers) are achievement, recognition, the work itself, responsibility and advancement/promotion opportunities and hygiene factors are contextual factors (dissatisfiers) are pay and benefits, policies and administration practices, supervision, interpersonal relations, working conditions and job security (Miner, 2006). *“These dissatisfiers, or hygiene factors, when appropriately provided, can serve to remove dissatisfaction*

and improve performance up to a point, but they cannot be relied upon to generate really positive job feelings or the high levels of performance that are potentially possible” (Miner, 2006, p. 50).

According to Herzberg, although contextual factors play a role, motivation factors are more instrumental in determining job satisfaction of personnel, who ultimately have a bigger stake to play in job processes. This theory implies that leaders need play a facilitation role in empowering staff to grow in their careers.

The expectancy theory, which was developed by Vroom in 1964 focuses on what organizations need to do to motivate staff to achieve for the organization as they pursue personal goals. Vroom opined that personnel make conscious choices based on prioritizing available alternatives in the order of the most desirable pleasure. *“According to the expectancy theory, human motivation is affected by anticipated rewards and costs; an employee will be motivated to work towards a particular goal, if it is perceived that a personal need will be satisfied” (Sims, 2002, p. 60).* Vroom subsequently emphasizes on the importance of staff perception on work, which is influenced by their perception on ability to accomplish the task, their perception on the benefit of the work to them and the perception on whether the completion of the task is commensurate with the desired outcomes.

Hence, according to Vroom, ethical leadership need to apply emotional intelligence (EI) in order to ensure the perceptions of staff on work remain positive and relevant. This implies that leaders play an empowering role where staff are helped to align personal goals with the organizational ones.

Herzberg’s and Vroom’s theories complement each other. This is because studies have shown that intrinsic motivation is important in enhancing the job satisfaction of staff and yet their perception on how the job fits within personal goals is an important factor of job satisfaction. Similarly, staff expectations are import factors of job satisfaction and employees’ perceptions towards the role their jobs in enhancing personal development need to remain positive. The two theories then imply that if ethical leadership is employed, staff also need to be ethical “followers” and self-leaders, who are concerned both about the welfare of their work and about their own career growth respectively.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Challenges of Career Advancement

According to Dialoke, Adighije and Nkechi (2017), *“Career advancement normally entails a clearly marked path of progression through the ranks of an organization” (p. 8).* Relatively speaking, all employees of an organization should have great potential and desire to make progress in life. Nevertheless, advancement seems to happen faster for some employees than for others, while it sometimes appears that some do not advance at all. One would wonder why some employees seem to be satisfied with their status quo for a long time, yet career advancement provides them with *“opportunity for long term success, higher pay, job security, and job satisfaction” (Dialoke, Adighije & Nkechi, 2017, p. 8).* Under normal circumstance, these outcomes of career advancement should motivate

people to make progress in their careers. The disparity between staff who progress and those who do not could be explained by reason that career advancement is influenced by both individual and organizational factors (Arokiasamy, et al., 2014, p. 275).

Career advancement is an important aspect of any employment. Many employees desire to grow from one level of responsibility to another, from one level of productivity to another and consequently from one level of income to another. One way of achieving career advancement is through promotion at work. However, promotion should not be desirable without commensurate commitment, responsibility, diligence, and productivity at work. Employees therefore need to be proactive at developing competences that build their capacity to excel at work.

Conversely, organizations need to work with policies which guide personnel on various dimensions of their work. Dialoke, Adighije and Nkechi (2017) found that *“there is a positive and significant correlation between career development and the performance of the non-academic staff... and also career advancement is positively correlated with motivation of the non-academic staff of the [studied] university”* (p. 8). Organizations that have policies on career advancement and that implement those policies can enhance staff morale. This is because career advancement *“is based on merit without regard for race, gender, age or ethnicity. Deserving cases become eligible for advancement. When employees get to know that each one of them has an equal chance of succeeding, it becomes easy for them to put in their best”* (p. 8). It is then necessary for organizations to ensure policies are comprehensively generated, reviewed, and implemented fairly.

This could be explained contextually because the ranking criterion for non-academic staff is usually vague for various reasons. While ranks could be existing – such as: administrative assistant, senior administrative assistant, chief administrative assistant, manager and others; or librarian, senior librarian and executive librarian among others; it is not usually clear what qualifications or competences are needed to move from one level to another. Is it added academic credentials? What if the acquired academic credentials are not related to the primary role of the staff? What about staff who never pursue additional academic credentials but demonstrate commitment to the organization and admirable work outputs?

2.2 Performance-Based Promotion

Some schools of thought suggest that promotion can be based on performance outputs of employees. For example, Mustapha and Zecharia (2013) opined that, *“Promotion opportunities are also an important aspect of a worker’s career and life. The university can use promotion opportunities as a reward for highly productive workers to exert greater effort; more satisfied workers are less likely to leave their employer, have lower rates of absenteeism and higher productivity”* (p. 25). This suggestion is appealing, but its implementation is challenging. While productivity in corporate organizations where returns are received in terms of numbers of transactions, amounts of money and other measurable indicators can be achieved and appraised, many service delivery units or organizations face staff appraisal challenges. In universities, there are many academic and non-academic units where measuring worker productivity is a daunting task.

In some cases, it is possible for Human Resource Managers to conduct surveys and receive supervisors' reports on workers' productivity. However, since promotion is accompanied by increase in salary, it may be difficult to determine the productivity thresholds that warrant promotion. This is especially so because many service delivery units do not generate direct revenues. Additionally, those which generate revenues are not necessarily profit making because revenues support delivery of services. Moreover, many services are not supervised by expert managers.

For example, universities offer services such as medical (through clinics), hospitality (through cafeterias and guest houses), primary and secondary schools, shops, and banking services among others. Although such units have been initiated to be income generating, studies have shown that these services have not been necessarily profitable (Mungathia, 2018; Munene 2019). The academic units have also not been financially stable due to low student numbers and inflated wage bills. One would ask: should a university guest house grow to be a hotel? Should a university clinic grow to be a dispensary in order to provide numerous promotion opportunities? Should tack shops grow to be supermarkets, should small banking services grow to be banks? How much time should be expected from such growth to be realized? On the academic side, should departments grow to be schools/faculties? Should centres grow to become institutes? Should campuses grow to universities? How long should such growth be expected to take place? Such questions should be addressed in strategic planning of the university. When identified strategies are well implemented, growth of various units could bring about promotion opportunities. But what would it take for such growth to be achieved?

A commitment to career advancement will enable steps toward achieving a better motivated workforce and a high performing organization. It also presents employees with opportunities to further their education and undergo training, thus strengthening employees' skill sets to receive consideration for a promotion and advance their career. (Dialoke, Adighije & Nkechi, 2017, p. 8)

Clearly, this requires ethical leadership to clearly share the strategic plan of the institution in order for staff to perceive expected competencies to which they should align their personal and organizational goals. Moreover, creating opportunities for training would enhance learning communities within university settings and thus promote long-life learning. Such working environments are likely to develop as incubators of great ideas for innovation.

2.3 Credential-Based Promotion

Employees' competences and qualifications are key determinants of performance. Universities may therefore need to create career advancement programs that empower personnel to continue on the desirable growth path. Commitment towards staff career advancement (or provision of promotion opportunities) has potential to boost workers' job satisfaction. According to Malik, Danish and Munir (2012), "*...in higher education, job satisfaction, particularly among administrators, has been sparsely examined, and cumulatively the studies in this area suggest there is little unity in understanding job satisfaction in a college*

or university context" (p. 230). Therefore, although most institutions have clear qualifications needed for non-academic staff to be employed in a job, they do not have clear advancement criteria. Moreover, academic credentials for non-academic staff are not required to be as high as those of the academic staff for equivalent ranks. This disparity continues to be a major "divide" between academic and non-academic staff. While the difference may be fathomable, what remains a challenge is the ambiguity of the specific credentials needed for some of higher ranks of non-academic staff. This ambiguity sometimes allows for negotiations, unfair competition, and dependence on "god-fathers".

The disparity can be addressed if equivalent promotion criteria required of academic staff is required for non-academic staff. For example, according to the Commission for University Education (CUE) promotion criteria, the requirements for academic personnel are clear, though discussions on the logic behind the weightings (such for co-published works) are an ongoing debate. The criterion for promotion of non-academic staff is not provided for by CUE. However, the need to create a harmonized criterion for the promotion of non-academic staff is long overdue. The criteria should take into consideration competences in leadership, supervision, administration and other aspects of service delivery. For example, the growth of a non-academic unit should be measured by its growth qualitatively and quantify as indicated by the quality of service delivery and/or revenue depending on the unit. Promotion criteria for non-academic staff should also consider the three mandates of a university including teaching, research and community engagement. Any proposed criterion need to be comparable to the CUE criterion of ranking academic staff as suggested in Table 1 below:

**Table 1: CUE's Promotion Criteria for Academic Staff and
 Proposed Promotion Criteria for Non-Academic Staff**

Cue's Criteria of Ranking Academic Staff		Author's Proposed Criteria of Ranking Non-Academic Staff	
Nomenclature	Qualifications	Nomenclature	Suggested Qualifications
Graduate Assistant /Research Assistant	Bachelors enrolled Registered/Qualified for Masters Teaching Competencies	Admin Assistant	Bachelors Registered/Qualified for Masters Administration competencies
Tutorial Fellow /Junior Research Fellow	Masters/equivalent Registerable for PhD	Senior Admin Assistant	Masters/equivalent Registerable for PhD
Lecturer /Research Fellow	PhD/equivalent or Masters with/and 40pts Publication 30pts Teaching & Instruction 20pts Administration responsibilities 10pts Community Engagement	Chief Admin Assistant/Assistant Manager	PhD/Equivalent Masters with/and 40pts Supervisory points 30pts Administrative Responsibilities 20pts Teaching & Instruction 10pts Community Engagement
Senior Lecturer /Senior Research Fellow	PhD/equivalent 50pts Publication 25pts Teaching & Instruction 10pts Professional/ Consulting 10pts Administration responsibilities 05pts Community Engagement	Manager	PhD/Equivalent 50pts Supervisory points 25pts Administrative Responsibilities 10pts Professional/ Consulting 05pts Teaching & Instruction 05pts Research 05pts Community Engagement
Associate Professor	PhD/equivalent 60pts Publication 20pts Teaching & Instruction 10pts Professional/ Consulting 05pts Administration responsibilities 05pts Community Engagement	Senior Manager/ Assistant Director	PhD/Equivalent 60pts Supervisory points 20pts Administrative Responsibilities 05pts Professional/ Consulting 05pts Teaching & Instruction 05pts Research 05pts Community Engagement
Professor	65pts Publication 15pts Teaching & Instruction	Director	PhD/Equivalent 65pts Supervisory points

	10pts Professional/ Consulting 05pts Administration responsibilities 05pts Community Engagement		15pts Administrative Responsibilities 05pts Professional/ Consulting 05pts Teaching & Instruction 05pts Research 05pts Community Engagement
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2.4 Key

The suggested criteria of promoting non-academic staff assumes that growth in supervision is a key indicator of career growth, but most non-academic staff need to participate in fulfilling all three mandates of a university, namely: teaching, research and community engagement (CUE 2014 Guidelines). The following are assumptions made by the author in proposing the promotion criteria for non-academic staff in Table 1 above.

- 1) Supervision points assume that the non-academic staff demonstrates leadership ability and grows their unit of service in size and productivity.
- 2) Administrative responsibilities (without supervision) include delegation, controlling, planning and organizing activities at work.
- 3) Professional Consulting assumes that the non-academic staff has identified an area of contribution and is able to create partnerships to exercise their expertise and benefit the institution.
- 4) Teaching and Instruction is for the purpose of bridging gaps between service delivery and academic units in order to understand the main client of the university, the student.
- 5) Research assumes that each unit (academic and non-academic) in the university needs to be run based on current research findings and that research funds can be solicited to enhance the effectiveness and efficiency of the units.
- 6) Community engagement assumes that the staff identifies the link between the university and the community and creates opportunities for meaningful engagement which includes (but not limited to) dissemination of research findings and the development of relevant services for the community.
- 7) It is important to note that the proposed path needs more discussions and scrutiny to determine the most desirable competences and achievement indicators among non-academic staff. (This is also true about the existing ranking criteria for academic staff, which needs revision according to the changing dynamics of academia). For example, in light of the daunting economic challenges facing universities, what competences may be required of both academic and non-academic staff in all ranks to enhance the financial sustainability of universities? Should all staff be required to attract funding? Such may need to be included in the ranking criteria.

Another thing to consider is whether all personnel should exhibit the same level of strength in a certain competency or whether diversity should be encompassed. Should all research, publish, teach and engage community uniformly or should personnel be allowed to earn the highest points in their areas of strength? If a staff (academic or non-academic) thrives more in administration, then their highest weighted points could be in that area (while still achieving the minimum required in publications) instead of expecting academic staff to have the highest points in publication points. The same would apply for other areas. This is a matter needing more attention by policy makers.

- Universities need to rethink whether they should engage semi-illiterate staff who have no interest for academic growth to offer services or whether they should outsource some service delivery or even build income generating service provision units with personnel who can also grow in pursuit of knowledge.

2.5 Integrated Promotion Model

The integrated promotion model is eclectic in nature and combines both competencies and academic credentials in ranking of personnel within university settings. While some argue that credentials may not be necessary, universities whose existence is the advancement of knowledge must be populated by staff who are both competent and knowledgeable.

Personnel in the university need to exercise ethical “followership” in order to make progress in their careers, which can only be achieved through the practice of self-leadership with the ultimate goal of making their units/institutions progress. On one hand, ethical followership is a moral-reflective process where decision making on moral behaviour is based on an interactive quadripartite process involving moral sensitivity (recognition), moral judgment, moral motivation and moral character (Rest, 1999). On the other, self-leadership, according to Stewart et al., citing Manz (1991), is *“a self-influence process and set of strategies that address what is to be done (e.g., standards and objectives) and why (e.g., strategic analysis) as well as how it is to be done... [it] incorporates intrinsic motivation and has an increased focus on cognitive processes”* (Stewart, et al., 2011, 188). In an institutional setting all workers need to participate in self-leadership as illustrated in Figure 1:

Figure 1: Application of Self-Leadership at Various Level of an Organization
(from Bryan & Kazan, 2012)

This process involves both cognitive and affective processes. The application of the integrated model implies that ethical leaders do not perceive themselves as self-sufficient in realizing the career advancement of personnel but as facilitators of an enabling environment where staff can thrive at work.

2.6 Contextual Issues in Promotion

There are contextual issues that may explain the progression or lack of career advancement among personnel. In a study conducted among six Christian universities (Mbogo, 2011), a comparison was made to investigate job satisfaction between those who had served between 1 and 5 years and those who had served between 6 and 25 years. The results showed a statistically significant difference in promotion mean scores among personnel who had served for fewer years (1-5) compared to those who had served for more years (6-25) ($U = 1758.50$, $z = -2.726$, $p < .01$, $r = -.25$). Those who had served longer had lower mean scores implying they were less satisfied with promotion opportunities. These findings could be demonstrative of ceiling levels on career progression among older personnel. What can universities do to ensure that staff do not feel stagnated in their career?

Firstly, staff development programs can provide opportunity for ongoing training in order to empower personnel to develop career paths within the institution. These are aligned to both their personal goals, and the mission and vision of their institutions in the light of stipulated strategic plan. Wachira (2016) found that universities need to enhance career advancement by developing non-academic staff in five areas: “work environment facilities available, technology development, staff training and development, policies and work systems (infrastructure) and number of middle level non-teaching staff working in campuses” (p. 104). Focus on these broad areas of career

development made staff to be focused on areas that will add value both to themselves and to their institutions. For that reason, it is necessary for ethical leadership to be intentional in providing and enhancing staff development policies and programs.

Secondly, university management need to create, implement and review policy to address career advancement issues among staff in an objective manner. This is because perceptions of personnel on fair treatment at work are of paramount significance. In Mbogo's study (in 2011), respondents indicated they experienced: *"inequitable treatment of personnel... ambiguity in the systems in the institutions [which] had caused decisions to be made unfairly... Procedures for promotion based... on who you know and who in the organization... the use of a negotiation system to determine salaries, while existing pay scales were overlooked... apparent discrimination"* (Mbogo, 2018, p. 274). In a study conducted on perceptions of staff on procedural justice related to *"rewards, pay, promotion and assignments"*, at a Scandinavian university, found that:

"...when perceptions of fairness changed, the self-rated health of employees also changed, for example those who experienced more fairness on average over the period studied reported better health.... changes in employees' health are related to changes in fairness perceptions, indicating that the health status of employees may also affect how employees feel treated at work." (University of East Anglia, 2016, p. 3, 5)

From the foregoing, fairness in the treatment of staff needs to be promoted within university settings. This should be done in light of statutory laws and guidelines given by the Commission for university education. Fairness should not just be in matters of salary, but also treatment across ranks, educational level, gender, ethnic affiliations and other socio-political variables.

3. Implications to Ethical Leadership

Ethical leadership is *"the demonstration of normatively appropriate conduct through personal actions and interpersonal relationships, and the promotion of such conduct to followers through two-way communication, reinforcement, and decision-making"* (Brown et al., 2005). With regards to career advancement of staff, ethical leaders operate with clear policies and guidelines stipulated in the statutes of the university. They seek to implement these policies fairly and consistently, reviewing them based recurrent statutory adjustments and contextual realities, in consultation with relevant authorities. Ethical leaders are therefore concerned about the welfare of all personnel and create an environment for the employee to thrive, being productive in their work and also growing in the career. This is effectively managed through dialogue. Hegarty asserts that ethical components include: *"gratitude, humility, justice, mercy and compassion, prudence and objectivity, magnanimity, integrity, and resilience"* (2018, p. 2). As such, ethical leaders all called up to offer solutions to potential pitfalls, apparent disparities and related career advancement issues that are likely to thwart the effective running of institutions.

In relation to both academic and non-academic staff and career advancement in higher education, ethical leadership would be concerned about the welfare of personnel ensuring system fairness. However, many university ranking systems are clear on the requirements of staff toward mobility from one rank to another. While some universities have ranks for non-academic staff, it is not clear what requirements allow movement from one level to another. There are various complexities that make that happen including 1) complex university systems 2) competences of personnel 3) academic qualifications of personnel 4) vague indicators of excellence (Mihelič et al., 2010, p. 33).

Being ethical is about playing fair, thinking about welfare of others and thinking about consequences of one's actions. However, even if one grows up with a strong sense for good or bad, the bad behaviour of others can undermine his ethical sense as well. Ethical leaders think about long-term consequences, drawbacks and benefits of their decisions. For the sake of being true to their own values and beliefs, they are prepared to compete in a different battle on the market, where the imperative is: Do what is right.

This implies that ethical leaders will endeavour to create systems that are effective. Further, it infers continuous policy development, guidelines clarification, prudent implementation and diligent monitoring and evaluation of the process. Hassan, et al., (2013) examined how ethical leadership and empowering leadership are related to leader-member exchange relations (LMX), affective commitment, and leader effectiveness among 259 subordinate staff working for both public and private managers. *"The results indicated that ethical leadership and empowering leadership have positive associations with LMX, subordinate affective commitment, and perception of leader effectiveness"* (p. 133). If non-academic staff have to be committed to their work and have positive attitudes towards their seniors, it is necessary for leaders to demonstrate genuine concern for their staff. As discussed earlier, this concern is not just limited to what the organization can do for staff but it is also about empowering staff to conceptualize what they can do for the organization. Ethical leaders are therefore committed to a two-way process that ensures collaboration and collegiality while respecting ranks in the work place. This in turn generates trust between leaders and staff. Kalshoven and Den Hartog (2009) found that *"...ethical leadership and especially fair behaviour is related to a shared prototype, which in turn is related to increased trust, and that is related to enhanced leader effectiveness"* (p. 113). Therefore, ethical leaders need to keep communicating plans, intentions and changes throughout the implementation process.

Finally, ethical leadership, just like staff, should continue with the process of self-leadership even when they have reached the pinnacle of their careers at their institution. This implies a process of self-evaluation within the changing university environments and hence continuous self-development of needed competencies to offer timely solutions. In this effort however, ethical leaders need to identify competencies that they are deficient in and that may not be tenable to pursue for timely action. In such situations, ethical leadership seeks to identify, develop, promote and deploy qualified and competent staff to complement their efforts, by either recruiting externally

or internally. For example, according to Munene (2019), universities need strong financial managers as opposed academics for financial sustainability. However, ethical academic leaders can identify such gaps and bridge them by developing competent teams for critical areas of survival and growth. Ethical leadership must therefore result to efficient and effective team leadership.

4. Recommendations

Self-leadership is an aspect that ought to be continuously practised by ethical leaders. This will contribute to the sustainability of universities as ethical leadership facilitates enabling working environments for non-academic staff. This implies that ethical leaders need to do the following:

- 1) Engage their non-academic staff in developing reasonable ranking criteria that encompasses the triad mandate of universities – teaching, research and community engagement.
- 2) Benchmark with other ethical leaders in both public and private universities to emulate and adapt best practice.
- 3) Partner with like-minded universities in resource exchange and networking especially in staff development programs.
- 4) Enhance the understanding of non-academic staff on the strategic plans of the university, their implementation matrix and their implications on personal career development.
- 5) Exercise fairness by adhering to set policies, reviewing policies and developing guidelines while constantly communicating changes to non-academic staff and collecting necessary feedback from staff for collective decision making.
- 6) Develop team leadership skills for optimum growth in the university.

5. Conclusion

Career advancement is an important aspect for the advancement of the university enterprise. Advancement policies must however be clear and elaborate for the non-academic staff to match the current achievement for ranking of the academic staff, even as both ranking criteria are scrutinized and revised considering dynamic contexts. This demands ethical leadership where collegial approaches are applied to enhance the growth of both staff and the universities themselves. Ethical leaders are likely to succeed when staff engage themselves in ethical followership, where personal interests for career growth do not overlook the growth interests of the university. Moreover, both ethical leaders and followers must practice self-leadership in order to grow universities to become centres of excellence where great ideas are incubated, birthed and nurtured innovatively.

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Rosemary Wahu Mbogo
CAREER ADVANCEMENT AND JOB SATISFACTION AMONG
NON-ACADEMIC STAFF IN UNIVERSITY SETTINGS AND IMPLICATIONS FOR ETHICAL LEADERSHIP

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